

Figure 4c: The 8 by 8 vāstu, PI 8.73-86.

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|----------------|---------------|----------------|
| 1 Brahmā | 19 Satya | 37 Roga |
| 2 Marīcaka | 20 Bhṛṣa | 38 Vāyu |
| 3 Vivasvant | 21 Antarikṣa | 39 Nāga |
| 4 Mitra | 22 Agni | 40 Mukhya |
| 5 Pṛthivīdhara | 23 Pūṣan | 41 Bhallāṭa |
| 6 Āpa | 24 Vitatha | 42 Soma |
| 7 Āpavatsa | 25 Gṛhakṣata | 43 Ṛgi |
| 8 Savitṛ | 26 Yama | 44 Adīti |
| 9 Sāvītri | 27 Gandharva | 45 Diti |
| 10 Indra | 28 Bhṛṅga | 46 Skanda |
| 11 Indrajit | 29 Mṛga | 47 Aryaman |
| 12 Rudra | 30 Pitṛ | 48 Jambha |
| 13 Rudradāsa | 31 Dauvārika | 49 Pilipiccha |
| 14 Īśa | 32 Sugrīva | 50 Carakī |
| 15 Parjanya | 33 Puṣpadanta | 51 Vidārī |
| 16 Jaya | 34 Pracetas | 52 Pūtanā |
| 17 Mahendra | 35 Asura | 53 Pāparākṣasī |
| 18 Sūrya | 36 Śoṣa | |

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	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	14	15
	37	13		5		7		16		
	36	12				6		17		
48	35			1		2		18	46	
	34	4						19		
	33	10		3		8		20		
	32	11				9		21		
	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22

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